

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	05	03	CAPE TOWN	S	33	54.2163	E	018	25.379
End	2022	05	31	WALVIS BAY	S	22	56.648	E	014	27.8653

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAINING OBJECTIVES

The objective of this leg was to study the microbiome of Benguela upwelling region. We focussed on both the southern and northern regions, with a specific focus on oxygen minimum zones and the nutrient budget. It is well known that the productivity resulting from upwelling regions produce large algae blooms, however very little is known about how the resident microbiome helps or hinders this. Our strategy was therefore to sample inshore, on shelf and just off shelf in the form of transects up the South African and Namibian coast so we could capture freshly upwelled waters (inshore), modified upwelled waters (shelf) and more nutrient depleted waters (offshore) so we can try to understand how the microbial loop adapts during these different stages. We were also interested in aerial transport especially from the Namib desert, and how (or if at all) this influences algal productivity. Finally, we introduced a few extra biogeochemical protocols that measured nutrient uptake (microbes + algae) as well as nutrient transformation rates at depth. This is in part due to a nutrient deficiency in the South African upwelling that we are trying to further understand. Our South African station included the use of a McLane pump at depth where there was no oxygen so we could capture the microbial community composition *in situ* without any contamination of oxygen. We also measured N₂O, a highly concentrated greenhouse gas, that we know is being produced in our south African stations. This data will help to parameterize a model of the Benguela so we may predict future scenarios in the region with more accuracy.

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Samuel AUDRAIN
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Yves TOURNON
3	CREW - Mecano	Laurent ROGNIAUX
4	CREW - Deck	David MONMARCHAND
5	CREW - Deck	Louis Wilmotte
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie Bain
7	CREW - Media	Maeva Bardy
8	GUEST - Artist	Kimerudi Motswai
9	GUEST - Observer	-
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Thomas LEEUW
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Nicole DAMES
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Céline DIMIER
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Mathilde BOURREAU
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Ndamonoghenda Mateus
15	SCIENCE - F – Chief Scientist	Emma ROCKE

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

(describe the stations and environments covered during the campaign, including figures as needed)

The northern and Southern Benguela upwelling regions were covered during this leg. The Benguela upwelling is one of four major Eastern Boundary upwelling systems (EBUS) in the world. Coastal upwelling is a major oceanic process driven by prominent currents, of which those within Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems are most important globally. These systems are present along the western shores of landmasses in the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans where they comprise vast regions of coastal ocean water. High productivity brings with it low to no oxygen zones which endanger the local ecosystem services. While macrofauna either die or move away, the microbiome in these areas remain active. We were interested in sampling different stages of the Benguela upwelling system to understand the evolution of the microbiome before, during and after an upwelling event and in these low oxygen zones. In addition to upwelling, we were also interested in describing the Orange River microbiome as well as any associated microplastics (Orange River transect), and the effects of desert aerial transport on marine productivity and associated microbes (Namib desert line). We sampled the wide shelf which extends into the Walvis ridge, where upwelling intensity is reduced, as a form of control transect. There was not enough time to samples the narrow shelf up by the Angolan border.

Figure 1. Location of sampling stations

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

(describe how the objectives were achieved and highlight preliminary findings and observations)

We successfully sampled all 15 stations we originally targeted, as well as all the protocols we planned on including during this leg. This included several additional biogeochemical protocols in addition to the mission microbiome protocols. These additional protocols focussed on the rates of nutrient uptake and nutrient recycling. A McLane pump was successfully deployed in the oxygen minimum zone at station 110. Preliminary results from the underway system indicate that we managed to cover all stages of an upwelling event, as well as some interesting diatom communities, the detailed results of which will come later.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

(Provide an overview of sampling activities on every day of the Campaign, indicating the number of deployments done for each type of event)

Station ###	Date, start YYYY-MM-DD	Latitude, start N dd.dddddd	Longitude, start E ddd.dddddd	UDW - Aerosols	UDW - Biogeochemistry	BGC – CAST – 0-1000	SML	SRF – PUMP	SRF – NET – WP11 20	SRF – NET – WP11 200	SRF – NET – Manta 330	EPI – CAST – 0-200	EPI – NET – WP11 20	EPI – NET – WP11 200	EPI – Régent 680	MESO – CAST – 0-1000	CAST – Trace Metals	VMP – Profile	TIA – Towed Array	BowPole	HTSRB
110	20220505	S 32°38.056'	E018°02.192'	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					X	
111	20220507	S 28°44.053'	E 016°20,666'	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X					X	
112	20220508	S 29°25.6877	E 015°14.89	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X		X			X	
113	20220510	S 29°48.4799	E 014°15.0266	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X		X	
114	20220512	S 26°47.079	E 013.06089	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X		X	
115	20220515	S 26°32.36	E 015.0571	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X					X	
116	20220516	S 26.33088	E 014.09419	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X		X			X	
117	20220518	S 23.50596	E 014.26737	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X					X	
118	20220519	S 23° 54.0949	E 13° 43.6412	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X		X			X	
119	20220520	S 24° 1.9321	E 13°1.4341	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X		X	
120	20220523	S 19° 11.7466	E 11°37.5523	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X					X	
121	20220524	S 18°48,541	E 012°48,301	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X					X	
122	20220526	S 21° 46.0252	E 012° 46.0252	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X		X	
123	20220527	S 21°34.0547	E 013°8.6225	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X		X			X	
124	20220528	S 20°80.085	E 013°20.711	x	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X					X	

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

Storage T°C
Box size
Chemical

+10	+10	+10	+4	+4	+4	-20	-20	-20	-80 #1	-80 #2	-80 #3
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Protocol	Container type												
DIC13	200-mL-Bottle	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
DICTA	500-mL-bottle	82	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
DINO	60-mL-Bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	99	0	0	0	0	0
HG-M	125-mL Bottle	0	74	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MTE-BP	125-mL Bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MTE-F	125ml bottle, Double Zip-lock	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NUT-2	20mLCryoV	0	0	0	0	0	0	98	0	0	0	0	0
MTE-T	125-mL Bottle	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HG-T	40mL bottle, Zip-lock	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MB320	4-mL-Vial	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	0
MB023	4-mL-Vial	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	0
MB<02	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	0
eDNA	Sterivex (whirlpak)	0	0	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	0
NP550	20-mL-vial	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NP045	4-mL-vial	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0	0	0	0
HG	Zip-lock	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PM	Zip-lock	0	0	32	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S320	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	64	0	0
S023	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	62	0	0
S<02	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	66	0	0
P320	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38	0	0
P023	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38	0	0
DGAS	ExeT 12mL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	172	0	0	0	0
D018	AmberVial-40mL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SAL	125-mL-bottle	0	55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NUT1	20-mL-cryoV	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HP	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	119	0
SG	5-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	74	0	0
FC	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	136
HC	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	110	0
SEM	petrislide	0	37	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
FM20	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3DEM20	50 mL falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E20	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0

S20	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0
PM20	Zip-lock	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MB20	4-mL-vial	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
CP50	Zip-lock	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
F200	250-mL-bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E200	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0
S200	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0
S200-L	5-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0
PM200	Zip-lock	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MB200	Zip-lock	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0
CP200	Zip-lock	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
F680	250-mL-bottle	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
F2000	250-mL-bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E2000	250-mL-bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0
E680	250-mL-bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
S680-L	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
SP300	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0
MP300	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0
CP300	petrislide	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S025-L	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	0	0	0
S520-L	5-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0
FM5	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E5	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SEM5	petrislide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AI	petrislide	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AS	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	0
AF	Zip-lock	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	0	0	0	0	0
TOC	30mL bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0